

**RECOMMENDATIONS FOR RESTRUCTURING OF CURRENT FINANCIAL SYSTEM IN
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Financial support for healthcare is a key component that forms the basis for its functioning and development. In the context of the Republic of Kazakhstan, this area is implemented through a diversified revenue structure that includes both state and extrabudgetary sources. The main channels of financing include allocations from the republican and local budgets, targeted funds from the Social Medical Insurance Fund (SMIF), contributions to voluntary insurance programs, revenues from the provision of paid medical services, as well as charitable and other revenues that do not contradict current legislation. This multi-channel model ensures the relative stability of the healthcare system in the face of changing external and internal factors.

Keywords: Healthcare management, financial system of healthcare, healthcare in Kazakhstan, financing of healthcare.

The totality of financial resources, as well as the methods of their accumulation and subsequent distribution, forms the so-called health care financing mechanism. It operates within the framework of state policy and covers a complex of economic relations between the main actors—state bodies, health care institutions, financial organizations, and the population. The effective functioning of this mechanism is crucial for ensuring equal access to quality healthcare services and improving the level of social protection for citizens [1].

Research into financial mechanisms in the healthcare system has a long tradition in domestic and foreign scientific literature. Analysis of sources shows that there are various approaches to defining the essence and structure of this mechanism. Some researchers interpret the financial mechanism as a set of forms and methods of organizing financial relations that ensure the formation and use of resources in the healthcare industry. From the perspective of the financial flow management model, the financial mechanism is viewed as a system for regulating interactions between entities involved in the provision of medical services, aimed at improving operational efficiency through the use of financial methods and instruments [2].

From the perspective of institutional analysis, researchers emphasize the multiplicity of mechanisms for using financial resources, which is due to the diversity of their sources. According to these observations, this leads to the coexistence of several economic entities with different goals and financing mechanisms within a single medical institution [3].

In turn, some foreign researchers of the healthcare financing system identify the predominance of budgetary and insurance components in the structure of healthcare financing in the Republic of Kazakhstan, while emphasizing the continuing significant share of direct expenditures by the population. The authors emphasize the need to reform existing resource allocation mechanisms, improve targeting, and optimize spending, especially in the context of the compulsory social health insurance (CSHI) system.

International experience highlights the need for a balanced approach to the development of a healthcare

financing mechanism, combining public, insurance, and private sources, with priority given to protecting households from excessive financial costs. In the context of the Republic of Kazakhstan, measures to strengthen the role of public finances, improve the compulsory health insurance system, and reduce the share of direct expenditures of the population on medical services appear to be relevant.

In order to disclose the mechanism of healthcare financing in Kazakhstan and identify areas for improvement, it is necessary to understand what a financial mechanism is. A financial mechanism is a system for managing financial relations and resources aimed at ensuring the effective functioning of healthcare.

Financial flows in the healthcare system ultimately go to medical organizations, which are the main users of the allocated resources. Accordingly, these resources are based on various sources of funding that determine the volume and structure of revenues. The diversity of funding sources in the healthcare system determines the existence of diverse mechanisms for their use, resulting in the coexistence of participants with different financial functions and tasks within a single medical institution [4].

Despite the increase in funding, the healthcare system continues to be dominated by budgetary and insurance sources, with a high share of private expenditure, indicating the need for a profound transformation of resource allocation mechanisms and increased efficiency of targeted financing in order to achieve the strategic goal of bringing healthcare expenditure to 5% of GDP by 2027.

During the study of healthcare system funding participants, a summary was created reflecting expenditure categories according to funding sources (Table 1). The structure presented allows us to visualize the role and distribution of the burden among the main participants in the system: the state, the Social Health Insurance Fund, the population, and other entities. This typology contributes to a better understanding of the principles of financial flow redistribution and serves as a basis for further analysis of the effectiveness of each of the schemes.

Categories of expenditure according to sources of funding

Expense category	Information sources	Main channels for receiving funds
Government funding and mandatory insurance programs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Budget reporting for the functional group “Healthcare” (national and local budgets); – Data on the implementation of the GOBMP and OSMS packages; – Reports on expenditures for drug provision. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Republican and local budgets; – Social health insurance fund resources.
Off-budget expenditures of the population and businesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Statistical bulletins of the National Statistics Bureau of the Republic of Kazakhstan: “On the volume of healthcare services provided”; “Household expenditure and income”; “Retail trade by product group.” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Paid services in the healthcare system; – Direct costs to citizens and the private sector.
Voluntary health insurance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Reports of the National Bank of Kazakhstan on insurance premiums and payments for voluntary medical insurance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Funds from voluntary insurance companies and contributions from the population.
International assistance and other external sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – OECD Creditor Reporting System database – Funds from international organizations (UNICEF, WHO, World Bank, etc.); – Financial support from donor countries, including non-OECD countries. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Grants, donations, and humanitarian aid; – Other legitimate sources in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

The healthcare financing mechanism is a complex, multi-level structure that includes a variety of funding sources, as well as a set of entities and subjects whose relationships are regulated by the state.

It should be noted that state financing mechanisms play a key role in the procurement of medical services in the Republic of Kazakhstan. The bulk of these funds is directed toward inpatient care, primarily in hospitals. At the same time, organizations providing preventive and additional medical services, including emergency care and air ambulance services, remain heavily dependent on state appropriations.

At the same time, private sector financing is focused primarily on supporting the pharmaceutical industry, polyclinics, and multidisciplinary private medical centers. The financial schemes used in the healthcare system are key organizational forms through which medical services are paid for and citizens' access to the healthcare system is ensured. Mandatory state financing covers both budgetary resources and funds from the mandatory social health insurance (MSHI) system. In contrast, voluntary and private forms of financing include household expenditures on voluntary health insurance, business expenditures on employee health protection, and direct personal expenditures by citizens—so-called “out-of-pocket” household expenditures. Out-of-pocket payments by the population for medical care are a very important indicator of the financial burden on the population in any country.

Given the problems identified, it seems appropriate to implement the following areas of institutional and economic reform:

1. Introduction of a co-financing model for certain types of outpatient care for citizens with average incomes, while maintaining full budgetary support for vulnerable groups. Co-financing should be understood as a mechanism for distributing the financial burden between the state and the population, whereby basic services (examinations, diagnostics, essential medicines) are covered by the GOBMP and OSMM systems, while extended or more comfortable services are partially

paid for by the patient. This contributes to more targeted spending and encourages more rational consumption of medical care.

2. Expanding tax incentives for employers and investors involved in the development of voluntary health insurance and medical infrastructure. Such measures will stimulate investment activity, attract resources to university clinics and medical research centers, and improve access to high-tech treatment methods.

3. Reducing indirect taxes (in particular, VAT) on medical services and medicines in order to improve the financial accessibility of medical care. In addition, it is proposed to stimulate the development of domestic pharmaceutical production as a key factor in reducing medicine prices.

4. Ensuring transparency and accountability in the use of OSMF funds by creating a digital platform based on the principles implemented in the ENPF. Such a system will allow insured persons to track their contributions online, see a list of paid services, and the level of FSMF participation in financing specific types of care.

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